

The role of oxygenated species in the growth of graphene, fullerenes and carbonaceous particles

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Abstract

The growth of carbonaceous materials was studied using a Kinetic Monte Carlo model that captures the growth and oxidation of six-member and partially-embedded five-member rings. A novel algorithm was used to resolve the migration of partially-embedded five-member rings. Circumcoronene molecules were grown at 1500 K and 1 atm in the presence of varying mole fractions of atomic and molecular oxygen and constant mole fractions of hydrogen and acetylene. Four regions of carbon growth associated with different carbonaceous products were identified. Graphene was formed in the presence of high mole fractions of atomic oxygen ($10^{-4} < X_{\text{O}} \leq 10^{-2}$). Fullerenes were formed in the presence of low mole fractions of atomic oxygen and high mole fractions of molecular oxygen ($X_{\text{O}} \leq 10^{-4}$ and $10^{-2} < X_{\text{O}_2} \leq 10^{-1}$). Low mole fractions of both atomic and molecular oxygen ($X_{\text{O}} \leq 10^{-4}$ and

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$X_{\text{O}_2} \leq 10^{-2}$) resulted in structures that became curved as time progressed. Small structures were found at the highest mole fractions of atomic oxygen ($X_{\text{O}} > 10^{-2}$). The production and consumption of partially-embedded five-member rings appear to explain the formation of the observed structures. The oxidation of partially-embedded five-member rings produces armchair sites that grow to form flat graphenic structures. Formation and subsequent embedding of partially-embedded five-member rings result in curved structures that resemble fullerenes.

Keywords: Graphene, Fullerenes, Carbonaceous particles, Kinetic Monte Carlo model

1. Introduction

The gas phase synthesis of carbonaceous materials is a low cost scalable approach for generating a range of useful products. Carbonaceous particles in the form of carbon blacks can be produced under adequately controlled conditions [1]. Graphene, a large single layer of six-member rings, and fullerenes, closed cage molecules containing alternating five- and six-member rings, can also be produced under specific conditions. Both have many novel applications [2–5]. Under other conditions, undesirable products like soot are produced. This material, which is another type of carbonaceous particle, is a human health concern and an atmospheric pollutant [6]. The effect of the chemical environment on the formation of carbonaceous particles, fullerenes and graphene is still not fully understood.

Carbonaceous particles, fullerenes and graphene can be produced simultaneously under different conditions. Carbonaceous particles are primarily

formed from polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) produced in oxygen deficient environments such as flames or pyrolysis reactors. There is strong evidence that the interaction of two PAHs leads to the inception of carbonaceous particles, but the identity of these PAHs, and the nature of their interactions, remain elusive [6]. Fullerenes can be produced alongside carbonaceous particles in arc discharge reactors [7]. Fullerenes can also be produced in regions of high temperature [8] and in the presence of oxidising species [9, 10] in low pressure benzene [8] and acetylene [11] flames. Fullerenes are thought to share common crosslinked intermediates with carbonaceous particles [8] that, instead of continuously gaining mass, embedded five-member rings until the structure becomes fully curved [8, 12, 13].

Graphene can also be produced alongside carbonaceous particles in the gas phase of plasma reactors among other methods [14]. In one setup, ethanol and argon are used in a microwave plasma reactor [15–21]. The presence of oxygen in the precursor was found to be necessary to produce significant amounts of graphene [16]. In another setup, mixtures of methane, hydrogen and argon have been used to produce graphene in a microwave plasma [22, 23] or an arc-discharge plasma at different pressures [24]. In this case, the yield of graphene was reported to increase with increasing hydrogen content in the mixture [22]. In non-plasma conditions, large molecules that resemble graphene have been detected alongside carbonaceous particles in low pressure acetylene flames [11].

The surface growth of carbonaceous materials in a chemical environment is typically described by the hydrogen-abstraction acetylene-addition mechanism, better known as HACA [25] mechanism. This reaction model has

been repeatedly used to study the surface growth of carbonaceous particles without discriminating the local chemical structure involved in each reaction [26–29]. Resolving the local chemical structure, commonly referred to as *sites*, has been shown to be necessary to predict the morphology of carbonaceous products [30]. For example, an acetylene addition can produce either a five- or a six-member ring depending on the site where the reaction takes place [31].

The interactions between carbonaceous materials and oxygenated species have been extensively studied, most typically in combustion experiments. Early experiments on carbon rods with molecular oxygen (O_2) showed that carbonaceous materials present different types of reactive site, resulting in the development the Nagle-Strickland-Constable (NSC) model [32]. Neoh and collaborators showed that in low concentrations of molecular oxygen, oxidation appears to be dominated by hydroxyl radicals (OH) [33–35], and that atomic oxygen (O) is unlikely to be a significant oxidiser in typical flame conditions. However, atomic oxygen has been detected in plasma reactors [36, 37] and in significant concentrations in plasma assisted combustion experiments [38]. These three species appear to play different roles in the oxidation of carbon materials. Molecular oxygen appears to be responsible for the oxidation of carbonaceous particles from the inside of the particles, while hydroxyl radicals are associated with surface oxidation [39–42]. Atomic oxygen has been suggested to contribute to the oxidation of resonantly stabilised radicals [43] as well as producing epoxy and ether groups on the basal planes of PAHs [44]. Those oxygenated groups possibly explain the different oxidation rates observed in recent oxidation experiments of carbon black

with molecular and atomic oxygen [42].

Modelling the surface growth and oxidation of carbonaceous materials using kinetic models is challenging. The large number of individual species present in a reactive environment result in a large number of equations to be solved. Two types of model have been used to address this issue. Semi-empirical models have been extensively used to study the surface growth and oxidation of carbonaceous particles [26–29, 39, 45–48]. Even though these models reproduce some of the integral properties of carbonaceous particles (*e.g.* volume fraction [29]), they do not resolve the structural transformations of the molecules present in the material. In contrast to this, detailed particle models keep track of the sites available on a molecular edge. The reactions in this kind of model represent the transformation of individual surface sites instead of the full molecule. Detailed particle models typically use a Kinetic Monte Carlo (KMC) method to simulate the reactions occurring at individual sites. These are commonly known as KMC models. These models have been used to study the growth of graphene sheets [49–51], the formation of carbonaceous particles [30, 52] and the growth of particle precursors [53, 54].

Detailed models have been used to study the interaction of oxygenated and graphenic molecules. Frenklach and collaborators [55–57] used a KMC model to study the oxidation of different rings on graphene edges. Their results suggest that molecular oxygen and hydroxyl radicals are responsible for the oxidation of six-member rings via the decomposition of oxyradicals. This reaction produces either a five-member ring or a partially-embedded five-member ring. They also showed that atomic oxygen is likely to be responsible for the oxidation of partially-embedded five-member rings [43]. The

Figure 1: Species associated with the oxidation of six-member rings [57] and partially-embedded five-member rings [43].

oxidation of six-member rings and partially-embedded five-member rings by different species is shown in Figure 1. Other detailed models have focused on the formation of oxygenated groups in molecules that are precursors for carbonaceous particles [58–61]. These studies suggest that oxygenated species can enhance the growth of carbonaceous materials by creating additional types of ring and types of site in the material.

Partially-embedded five-member rings play an important role in the growth and oxidation of graphene, fullerenes and carbonaceous particles. Frenklach and collaborators suggested that these rings participate in the growth of graphene sheets by creating additional sites where six-member rings can grow [51]. Once formed, these rings participate in transformation processes that change the morphology of the structure. These are illustrated in Figure 2. Firstly, partially-embedded five-member rings are able to migrate around the edge facilitated by a hydrogen abstraction reaction. This process allows the rings to be positioned on either the edge or the corner of molecules. However, the kinetics of the migration reaction favour the edge position [62]. Secondly, rings occupying an edge position can become fully-embedded leading to the formation of curved polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (cPAHs) [51, 52, 63]. Recently, the recombination of partially-embedded

Figure 2: Migration and embedding of partially-embedded five-member rings [62].

five-member rings and neighbouring seven-member rings has been suggested as a possible mechanism for the formation of graphenic structures [64, 65].

The morphology of PAHs is also thought to play an important role in the inception of carbonaceous particles. Recently, two types of radical have been suggested as possible species that could participate in inception processes. First, delocalised π -radicals, which are associated with an odd number of six-member rings [66], delocalise their radical behaviour around the molecular structure giving them additional stability at high temperatures [67]. Second, localised π -radicals [68], which localise their radical character around edge five-member rings and partially-embedded five-member rings. Both types of radical have been suggested to form stable bonds with other PAHs and rate constants for these processes have been calculated [68–71]. Species with all of these structures have been experimentally observed in carbonaceous particles with different levels of hydrogen content and embedding using atomic force microscopy [72].

The interactions between oxygenated species and different carbonaceous materials have been studied mostly in combustion experiments. However, few studies have focused on conditions that favour the production of materials like graphene or fullerenes. A systematic study on the combined effect of surface growth in the presence of different oxygenated species is still missing.

The **purpose of this paper** is to investigate the effect of the oxygenated species on the formation of carbonaceous particles, fullerenes and graphene. A detailed KMC model is used to simulate the oxidation and growth of molecules in the presence of constant mole fractions of hydrogen and acetylene, and varying mole fractions of atomic and molecular oxygen. Two improvements are made to the model. First, the model is expanded to include the oxidation of partially-embedded five-member rings and six-member rings with rates calculated using a steady-state approximation. Second, a new numerical algorithm is introduced for the efficient simulation of the migration of partially-embedded five-member rings whilst retaining accurate growth and oxidation rates.

2. Methodology

2.1. Kinetic Monte Carlo model

Kinetic Monte Carlo models are useful to study the growth and oxidation of carbonaceous materials because they keep track of the sites that determine the reactivity of the molecules. These sites are allowed to react based on a set of reaction rules that are assumed to be a function of the site type. This gives these models the ability explore the transformation of different structures beyond typical gas phase chemical kinetic mechanisms.

In this work we use the *MOpS Particle Simulator* [73] to track the evolution of molecules in different chemical environments. The details of the model have been described previously [53]. In this work we improve the model by adding new processes for the oxidation of partially-embedded five-member rings and six-member rings using published rates from the litera-

ture [43, 55, 57]. The numerical performance of the model is also improved by including a new algorithm to describe the migration of partially-embedded five-member rings more efficiently. The algorithm was developed to be exact (*i.e.* it has no effect on the results calculated by the model), yet reduced computational times by more than an order of magnitude for all simulated cases. A complete description of the individual reactions, the process rates and the new migration algorithm is given in the Supplementary Material.

2.2. Parameter space

Most detailed models have focused on the growth and oxidation of carbonaceous materials in isolated conditions [43, 56, 57]. The few studies that have considered the competition between growth and oxidation have done so in the context of combustion [58–61]. A systematic parameter sweep to investigate the competition between growth and oxidation is still missing in the literature. To begin to address this gap, the chemical conditions selected in this work have been chosen to consider a constant potential for the growth of carbonaceous materials while varying the potential for both the oxidation of six-member rings and partially-embedded five-member rings.

The oxidation of six-member rings is dominated by two species: molecular oxygen and hydroxyl radicals. However, hydroxyl radicals participate in hydrogen abstraction reactions [74–76] that promote surface growth. Molecular oxygen has a high energy barrier for the same reaction [43] making its contribution to growth processes negligible. For this reason, molecular oxygen was selected for this study. Atomic oxygen was selected as a second oxidising species because it is known to attack partially-embedded five-member rings.

It is desired to study conditions that are relevant to a wide range of

experimental scenarios including fuel-rich flames, plasma and pyrolysis reactors. The parameter space therefore spans several orders of magnitude. The conditions used in the study are as follows: The mole fractions of species that contribute to growth were held constant at $X_{\text{H}} = 0.01$ and $X_{\text{H}_2} = X_{\text{C}_2\text{H}_2} = 0.1$. These conditions have been widely used to study typical growth environments [51, 64, 77]. Likewise, temperature and pressure were held constant at 1500 K and 1 atm and the simulation time held constant at 5 ms, consistent with previous studies [51, 57, 64, 77]. The mole fractions of atomic and molecular oxygen were varied in log-scaled intervals covering the ranges $10^{-8} \leq X_{\text{O}} \leq 10^{-1}$ and $10^{-6} \leq X_{\text{O}_2} \leq 10^{-1}$. The balance of the reaction mixture was argon.

The KMC model was used to simulate the oxidation and growth of an ensemble of 300 circumcoronene ($\text{C}_{54}\text{H}_{18}$) molecules at each condition. The software [73] used in this study is designed to simulate the simultaneous evolution of all molecules in the ensemble, including processes arising from interactions between the molecules, *e.g.* coagulation. However, in this particular case, the interaction between molecules was not considered and equivalent results could be achieved by simulating the evolution of each molecule individually. Averages and size distributions were calculated over each ensemble of molecules.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Regions of carbon growth

The growth of the molecules resulted in different morphologies in the different chemical environments sampled by the parameter space. However,

small variations in the mole fractions of molecular and atomic oxygen resulted in similar structures. This allowed us to divide the parameter space in four regions of carbon growth, where each region is associated with the observation of different carbonaceous structures: (1) large cPAHs, (2) small cPAHs, (3) large flat molecules, and (4) small molecules.

Figure 3 shows the average number of carbons observed in each molecule at the end of each simulation. The edges of the four regions of carbon growth are indicated with dashed lines. Experimental data for flames that produce carbonaceous particles [35, 61], fullerenes [78] and large flat molecules that resemble graphene [79] are shown (and are joined by continuous lines to guide the eye). Symbols are only shown for conditions that had sufficient hydrogen and acetylene to sustain the growth of carbonaceous structures. The geometry of representative molecules sampled from each region are also shown. The geometry of the full set of molecules is available in the Research Data associated with this work.

Region 1 (bottom left of Fig. 3) encompasses the lowest mole fractions of atomic and molecular oxygen, $10^{-8} \leq X_{\text{O}} \leq 10^{-4}$ and $10^{-6} \leq X_{\text{O}_2} \leq 10^{-2}$. The molecules in Region 1 contained an average of 300 carbon atoms. The molecules were mostly flat at early times, but became curved as simulations progressed. This can be seen in the representative structures in Fig. 3. Although the observed structures were large cPAHs, the main product in Region 1 will be carbonaceous particles. There is strong evidence that carbonaceous particles are formed by the interaction of two intermediate (and unknown) PAHs [6]. These interactions were not part of the scope of this study and the possibility to form carbonaceous particles was not included in

the current model. However, the molecules in this region spend significant time in the reaction environment before becoming curved. During this time the molecules could form carbonaceous particles. Most premixed sooting flames lie in Region 1. The maximum concentrations of molecular and atomic oxygen appear on the upstream side of the flame front, whilst the maximum concentrations of hydrogen and acetylene appear within the flame. This is represented as a movement towards the bottom left of Fig. 3. Two example flames in Fig. 3 are fully contained in Region 1: a sooting acetylene/air flame [61, 81] and the methane/oxygen experiments by Neoh [35]. The latter is included to highlight that oxidation by hydroxyl radicals becomes significant in flames with low mole fractions of molecular oxygen ($X_{\text{O}_2} < 10^{-5}$). Two other experiments are partially contained in this region and will be discussed below.

Region 2 (bottom right of Fig. 3) encompasses low mole fractions of atomic oxygen and high mole fractions of molecular oxygen, $10^{-8} \leq X_{\text{O}} \leq 10^{-4}$ and $10^{-2} < X_{\text{O}_2} \leq 10^{-1}$. The molecules in Region 2 contained an average of 150 carbon atoms. The structures in this region were highly curved and smaller than those in Region 1. Most of the structures became curved at short times. This can be seen in the representative structures in Fig. 3. The structures in this region resembled open caged fullerenes. Closed caged structures could not be produced in the simulations because no process to close the molecular structure was included in the current model. The interpretation of these observations is that the main product in Region 2 will be fullerenes. These observations are consistent with the experimental evidence presented in Fig. 3, where both carbonaceous particles and fullerenes

have been reported in the low pressure acetylene/oxygen [8, 11] and benzene/oxygen flames [9, 82, 83] that straddle Region 1 and Region 2.

Region 3 (middle of Fig. 3) encompasses high mole fractions of atomic oxygen and spans the full range of mole fractions of molecular oxygen in Fig. 3, $10^{-4} < X_{\text{O}} \leq 10^{-2}$ and $10^{-6} \leq X_{\text{O}_2} \leq 10^{-1}$. Region 3 is characterised by the highest average number of carbons per molecule: the molecules in Region 3 contained an average of 500 carbon atoms at $X_{\text{O}} = 10^{-3}$ and 600 carbon atoms at $X_{\text{O}} = 10^{-2}$. At high values of molecular oxygen ($X_{\text{O}_2} > 10^{-2}$) the molecules in Region 3 showed a lower number of carbons (approximately 300) per molecule due to oxidation. The structures in Region 3 were significantly larger than in the other regions. Most of the molecules were flat throughout the simulation. This can be seen in the representative structures in Fig. 3. The largest molecules were sampled at the higher mole fractions of atomic oxygen ($X_{\text{O}} = 10^{-2}$). To our knowledge this is the first time that such large structures have been obtained in a model that allows for the inclusion of curvature as a result of competing oxidation and surface growth. The preferred structure in this region is graphene. The high mole fractions of atomic oxygen that characterise this region make the synthesis of graphene in typical flame conditions unlikely. The only flame that appears to be close to this region is the low pressure acetylene/oxygen flame [11, 79] that reported the presence of large flat molecules in these conditions. However, this observation makes an argument for the production of graphene in other environments. Plasma experiments [*e.g.* 16, 17, 20, 37, 84] are known to form large numbers of oxygen radicals and ions that could perhaps explain the production of graphene. One of the challenges for these processes is to improve the prediction and

detection of species formed in the plasma to explain the production of new materials.

Lastly, Region 4 (top of Fig. 3) encompasses the highest mole fractions of atomic oxygen and spans the full range of mole fractions of molecular oxygen in Fig. 3, $X_{\text{O}} > 10^{-2}$ and $10^{-6} \leq X_{\text{O}_2} \leq 10^{-1}$. This region was characterised by a reduction in size of the molecules, despite the presence of hydrogen and acetylene. The molecules in Region 4 were flat and decreased in size during the simulations. This can be seen in the representative structures in Fig. 3.

Two opposite effects are clearly seen on the structures shown in Fig. 3. Molecular oxygen contributes to the integration of curvature while atomic oxygen inhibits it. The mechanism by which these two species lead to one process or the other appears to be related to the production and consumption of partially-embedded five-member rings and is discussed in the following sections.

Figure 3: Average number of carbons in each molecule versus mole fraction of atomic and molecular oxygen. Four regions of carbon growth (1 to 4) are indicated with dashed lines. Representative structures sampled from each region, at conditions indicated with open symbols, are shown. Experiments for which it is possible to estimate the mole fractions of atomic and molecular and oxygen are also shown. These correspond to: (◆) plasma ignition experiment [80], (▼) acetylene/oxygen low pressure flame [79], (●) benzene/oxygen low pressure flame [78], (▲) methane/oxygen flame [34] and (■) ethylene/air sooting flame [61]. Plasma ignition experiment is indicated with a dagger (†). Low pressure conditions (2.7kPa) are indicated with an asterisk (*).

3.2. Size distributions

The consideration of the average number of carbons per molecule allowed a straightforward comparison between the different regions of carbon growth. However, to have a more complete picture of the predicted structures, it is necessary to analyse the evolution of the size distribution of the sampled species as a function of the chemical conditions.

Figure 4 shows the molecular mass distributions of the sampled molecules halfway through (2.5 ms) and at the end (5.0 ms) of each simulation. Kernel density estimates (calculated using Seaborn with a Gaussian kernel and optimal bandwidth [85]) were used to estimate the continuous distribution functions shown in Fig. 4 from the masses of the molecules sampled by the KMC simulations.

The mass distributions sampled in Region 1 at 2.5 ms were centred around 2,000 a.m.u. with maximum values of approximately 4,000 a.m.u. By 5.0 ms the distributions were centred around 5,500 a.m.u. and presented a tail that extended up to 10,000 a.m.u. The molecules in these tails did not show any particular morphological difference in their structure other than being larger than the other molecules sampled in Region 1. They had a similar number of embedded five-member rings and similarly few hydrogen atoms.

Region 2 showed very similar mass distributions at both simulation times. The distributions were centred at 2,000 a.m.u. with a range extending from 1,000 to 3,000 a.m.u. The similarity of the mass distributions is an indication that the growth of these molecules is not significant after 2.5 ms. This effect can be explained by the decrease in the number of sites available for growth as the structure becomes highly curved.

Figure 4: Molecular mass distribution of molecules versus mole fraction of atomic and molecular oxygen. Simulation times of 2.5 and 5.0 ms are shown in blue and orange. Four regions of carbon growth (1 to 4) are indicated with dashed lines.

The mass distributions sampled in Region 3 increased in width during the simulations. At 2.5 ms the distributions were centred around 2,000 a.m.u. with a range extending to approximately 4,000 a.m.u. However, at 5.0 ms the distributions showed ranges extending to 13,000 a.m.u. at $X_{\text{O}} = 10^{-3}$ and extending to more than 16,000 a.m.u. at $X_{\text{O}} = 10^{-2}$. The only exception to these large distributions appeared at $X_{\text{O}_2} = 10^{-1}$, $X_{\text{O}} = 10^{-3}$, where the distribution showed a maximum value of 6,000 a.m.u. The large maximum values are indicative of the growth of large structures. These large structures were observed to be flat or slightly curved. Region 4 showed distributions centred at masses of less than 1,000 a.m.u. but with long tails composed of a few large molecules up to 7,000 a.m.u. in size appearing between 2.5 ms and 5.0 ms. The molecules in the tails of the distribution were smaller than, but otherwise similar to those observed in Region 3 at 5.0 ms.

The residence time has different effects on the mass distribution of the molecules in each region. This can be seen by comparing the distributions of Regions 1 and 3 in Fig. 4. At 2.5 ms the mass distributions in each region are similar. However, the mass distributions are significantly different at 5.0 ms, with Region 3 showing significantly larger molecules. The integration of curvature appears to be crucial in controlling the surface growth of carbonaceous structures. This can be observed in the mass distributions in Region 2, which did not change after 2.5 ms.

3.3. Inclusion of curvature

The curvature of carbonaceous nanostructures is caused by the presence of fully-embedded five-member [51] rings and seven-member [86] rings. In the extreme case, the presence of embedded five-member rings can lead to

the formation of closed caged fullerenes. In the absence of embedded five-member and seven-member rings, the molecules take the form of large sheets of six-member rings that resemble graphene.

Figure 5 shows the average number of fully-embedded five-member rings per molecule at 2.5 ms and 5.0 ms. The figure shows that, except at the highest mole fractions of atomic oxygen in Region 4, five-member rings are embedded in the molecules during the simulations.

Figure 5: Average number of fully-embedded five-member rings per molecule at (a) 2.5 ms and (b) 5.0 ms.

The molecules from Region 1 showed an average of 6 and 11 fully-embedded five-member rings at 2.5 ms and 5.0 ms, respectively. In this region the molecules became increasingly curved during the simulations. At low concentrations of oxygenated species, the molecules steadily embed five-member rings and gain curvature. This has also been observed in earlier work [53].

At 2.5 ms, Region 2 already shows structures that contain an average of 11 embedded five-member rings per molecule, where the first molecule to

reach this value was observed after only 1.1 ms. At 5.0 ms, every part of the region has an average of 11 embedded five-member rings. Molecular oxygen in the presence of favourable conditions for surface growth (hydrogen and acetylene) provides an additional pathway for the inclusion of five-member rings. This agrees with the observations of fullerenes sampled from diffusion flames [10] where it was suggested that the presence of molecular oxygen enhances the formation of curved structures.

Region 3 shows a trend similar to that in Regions 1 and 2, but with much slower inclusion of embedded five-member rings. At 2.5 ms the molecules presented an average of only 1 and 0 embedded five-member rings at $X_{\text{O}} = 10^{-3}$ and $X_{\text{O}} = 10^{-2}$ respectively. By 5.0 ms the number of embedded rings had reached 6 and 2 for the same conditions. It appears that for carbonaceous structures subject to HACA growth, the probability of embedding a partially-embedded five-member ring, and thus including curvature, increases with residence time.

The majority of the molecules in Region 4 did not appear to embed curvature at any time. The small structures that characterise this region were not large enough to fully-embed a five-member ring before being oxidised. However, in our study we were unable to find a set of conditions where molecules kept growing without at least some molecules including curvature after some time. This observation, although not surprising, has profound implications for the production of defect free graphene.

3.4. Mechanism for the formation of carbonaceous materials

Partially-embedded five-member rings play a crucial role in the formation of the different carbon structures discussed in this work. Figure 6 shows pro-

Figure 6: Mechanism of the formation of carbonaceous particles, fullerenes and graphene from partially-embedded five-member rings. Black arrows show processes that are present in all conditions. Blue arrows show processes that favour the production of fullerenes. Red arrows show processes that favour the production of graphene. Orange arrows show the crosslinking of partially-embedded five-member rings. Crosslinking was not studied in this work but has been suggested by other studies [67, 68].

cesses that produce, transform and consume partially-embedded five-member rings. Under different conditions these processes can explain the formation of graphene, fullerenes and carbonaceous particles. The production of these

rings can happen via three processes shown in the top row of the figure: (i) bay closure, (ii) HACA growth neighbouring five-member rings occupying edge positions and (iii) the oxidation of free-edge six-member rings by molecular oxygen. These processes form two different types of partially-embedded five-member rings (second row of Fig. 6), where the partially-embedded five-member ring can occupy either an edge position (left) or a corner position (right). Once formed, these structures can interconvert via ring migration processes. Previous studies have shown that the edge position is kinetically favoured [62].

The third row of Fig. 6 shows the processes that consume partially-embedded five-member rings. The bay closure and HACA processes (marked with a dagger, †) contribute to the inclusion of curvature via bay-capping of partially-embedded five-member rings occupying edge positions [51, 63, 77]. Oxidation by atomic oxygen (marked with a double dagger, ‡) and the recombination of partially-embedded five-member rings next to seven-member rings (not shown) remove partially-embedded five-member rings occupying corner positions without introducing curvature. A fifth process (crosslinking, orange) is discussed later. The recombination of partially-embedded five-member rings next to seven-member rings (shown in the Supplementary Material, Table 1, process S27) appeared to be unimportant due to the infrequent sampling of the processes (corresponding to less than 2% of the processes that removed partially-embedded five-member rings at any given point in the parameter space). The oxidation of partially-embedded five-member rings occupying corner positions by molecular oxygen is not favoured (marked with a turned dagger †) [43], whereas oxidation by atomic oxygen (‡) leaves

behind an armchair site that can undergo subsequent HACA growth as shown in Fig. 6.

In KMC models, the number of times each process is sampled is proportional to the rate of that process. In this work, the contribution of the chemical environment to growth processes was held constant by maintaining fixed values of the C_2H_2 , H and H_2 mole fractions, temperature and pressure, while the contribution to oxidation processes varied as a function of location in the O–O₂ parameter space. Figure 7 shows the number of sampled processes that produce (top row of Fig. 6) and consume (third row of Fig. 6) partially-embedded five-member rings across the O–O₂ parameter space. The bars have been divided to show the contribution of each process. The number of sampled processes for six-member ring growth are also shown.

The different regions of the parameter space show different behaviours. In Region 1 the formation of partially-embedded five-member rings was dominated by HACA (blue) and bay closure (green) processes. This region also showed an increase in the production of partially-embedded five-member rings via oxidation (red) of six-member rings as the mole fraction of molecular oxygen increased. The consumption of partially-embedded five-member rings in this region was dominated by HACA (blue) and bay closure (green) processes that result in curved structures. The number of six-member ring growth processes (orange) sampled in this region was the second highest, exceeded only by Region 3.

Region 2 showed increased production of partially-embedded five-member rings due to oxidation (red) by molecular oxygen. The consumption of these rings was mainly driven by HACA (blue) and bay closure (green) processes

Figure 7: Number of sampled processes in each simulation of 300 molecules. The first bar in each plot shows processes that produce partially-embedded five-member rings. The second bar shows processes that consume partially-embedded five-member rings. The bars are divided to show the contributions by HACA (blue), bay closure (green) and oxidation (red). The third bar shows processes that produce six-member rings (orange). Four regions of carbon growth (1 to 4) are indicated with dashed lines.

forming fully-embedded five-member rings. This increased production of partially-embedded five-member rings is consistent with previous work [57]. The low number of six-member ring growth processes (orange) sampled in this region is a consequence of the rapid embedding of curvature and the consequent reduction in the number of sites available for further HACA growth.

In Region 3, partially-embedded five-member rings were produced by HACA (blue), bay closure (green) and six-member ring oxidation (red) processes. The number of sampled oxidation processes increased as the mole fraction of molecular oxygen increased. The consumption of partially-embedded five-member rings was mainly due to oxidation (red) by atomic oxygen, with this process becoming more dominant as the mole fraction of atomic oxygen increased. The armchair sites produced by the oxidation (red) of partially-embedded five-member rings by atomic oxygen allow further growth without the inclusion of curvature. This is consistent with the observation that Region 3 sampled the highest number of six-member ring growth processes (orange) of all regions, with the number of sampled processes only notably decreasing at very high mole fractions of molecular oxygen ($X_{O_2} > 10^{-2}$). It is possible that atomic oxygen produced in plasma reactors contributes to the formation of graphene following these processes.

Region 4 sampled a large number of oxidation (red) processes that both produced and consumed partially-embedded five-member rings, alongside a significant number of six-member ring growth processes (orange) consistent with the production of armchair sites by the oxidation (red) of partially-embedded five-member rings by atomic oxygen. The net effect was a reduction in the size of the molecules during the simulations in Region 4.

The combination of processes that produce and consume partially-embedded five-member rings provides a possible explanation for the formation of fullerenes and graphene. In the absence of atomic oxygen, high mole fractions of molecular oxygen result in the production of additional partially-embedded five-member rings that can become fully-embedded after migration processes move them to edge positions. This results in curved structures, with an associated decrease in the number of sites that are available for reaction. This reduces the rate of growth and results in conditions that are favourable for the formation of fullerenes. Crosslinking with other carbonaceous molecules may be another process that contributes to the formation of fullerenes [8]. In the presence of atomic oxygen, partially-embedded five-member rings occupying a corner position can be oxidised to produce armchair sites that can subsequently grow via a HACA addition. This results in larger flat molecules that resemble graphene. These processes are indicated in Fig. 6 with blue and red arrows showing processes that we have discussed in connection with the formation of fullerenes and graphene respectively. There is also evidence for the formation of graphene in oxygen-free plasma reactors [22, 23]. This suggests that there must also be other mechanisms that prevent the inclusion of curvature in the molecules. A possible pathway could be the consumption of partially-embedded five-member rings due to ring enlargements caused by reactions with species that add a single carbon atom (*e.g.* methyl radicals) [87]. This process could convert five-member rings into six-member rings as previously suggested by Whitesides and Frenklach [51].

The orange arrows on Fig. 6 indicate crosslinking processes between (as yet unknown) structures. Although these processes are not simulated in

the current KMC model, they are believed to occur during the formation of carbonaceous particles and may be related to the presence of five-member rings. Many structures containing five-member rings have been shown to be able to form localised π -radicals [68]. The structure containing the partially-embedded five-member ring occupying a corner position (right, second row of Fig. 6) is an example of such a radical. It has been shown that the crosslinking of large localised π -radicals (from approximately 400 a.m.u.) results in stable bonded and stacked structures [68], that multiple localised π -radicals are possible within a single structure and that the concentrations of localised π -radicals are potentially significant at 1400–1500 K [70], leading to the suggestion of localised π -radicals as possible candidates to explain the inception of carbonaceous particles. Under conditions that slowly consume partially-embedded five-member rings (Region 1), as opposed to rapidly embedding the rings (Region 2) or oxidising them (Region 3), the molecules are likely to have enough time to form localised radical sites and interact with other molecules. Both of these observations are consistent with the pressure dependency of the different products: lower pressures drastically reduce the formation of carbonaceous particles, favouring the formation of fullerenes and graphene. This mechanism for the formation of carbonaceous particles via the collision of localised π -radicals needs further investigation.

4. Conclusions

A KMC model was used to study the growth of carbonaceous structures under different chemical conditions. The model includes processes for growth and for the oxidation of six-member rings and partially-embedded

five-member rings, and uses a new algorithm for the efficient simulation of the migration of partially-embedded five-member rings around the edge of the molecules. The mole fractions of hydrogen and acetylene were held constant at $X_{\text{H}} = 0.01$ and $X_{\text{H}_2} = X_{\text{C}_2\text{H}_2} = 0.1$, whilst the mole fractions of atomic and molecular oxygen were varied in range $10^{-8} \leq X_{\text{O}} \leq 10^{-1}$ and $10^{-6} \leq X_{\text{O}_2} \leq 10^{-1}$. The balance of the reaction mixture was argon.

The model was used to simulate the change in the structure of 300 circumcoronene ($\text{C}_{54}\text{H}_{18}$) molecules at each set of conditions. It was observed that atomic and molecular oxygen, which preferentially oxidise five-member and six-member rings respectively, have different effects on the size and morphology of the resulting carbonaceous structures. Four different regions of carbon growth, each of which is associated with processes that produce and consume partially-embedded five-member rings, were observed:

- In conditions with significant mole fractions of atomic oxygen ($10^{-4} < X_{\text{O}} \leq 10^{-2}$) and the full range of mole fractions of molecular oxygen ($X_{\text{O}_2} \leq 10^{-1}$), the oxidation of partially-embedded five-member rings produces arm-chair sites that participate in further growth processes. This produces large and flat molecules that keep growing as time progresses. This region is associated with the production of graphene.
- In conditions with significant mole fractions of molecular oxygen ($X_{\text{O}_2} > 10^{-2}$) and low mole fractions of atomic oxygen ($X_{\text{O}} \leq 10^{-4}$), the oxidation of six-member rings produces additional partially-embedded five-member rings that become rapidly embedded and formed highly curved structures. This region is associated with the production of fullerenes.

- In conditions with high mole fractions of atomic oxygen ($X_{\text{O}} > 10^{-2}$) and the full range of mole fractions of molecular oxygen ($X_{\text{O}_2} \leq 10^{-1}$), the oxidation of both six-member rings and partially-embedded five-member rings resulted in a reduction in the size of the simulated molecules.
- In conditions with low mole fractions of both molecular and atomic oxygen ($X_{\text{O}_2} \leq 10^{-2}$ and $X_{\text{O}} \leq 10^{-4}$) the simulated molecules became curved and grew slowly resulting in molecules with intermediate sizes. The possibility is raised that the slow inclusion of curvature in this region allows the formation of localised π -radicals in partially-embedded five-member rings. These radicals have been suggested to participate in the formation of carbonaceous particles [68].

The regions of carbon growth with low mole fractions of atomic oxygen agree well with known observations of the appearance of carbonaceous particles and fullerenes. The other regions seem unlikely to be observed in typical flame environments. However, processes associated with an increased production of atomic oxygen such as plasma reactors may operate at such conditions. This could contribute to the production of graphene in such processes.

The production and consumption of partially-embedded five-member rings appears to be important in explaining the formation of graphene, fullerenes and carbonaceous particles. These rings have been observed experimentally [72]. Further work is necessary to understand their role with respect to the viability of crosslinking in different chemical environments.

Research data

The source code for the KMC model [73] used in this paper is available on GitHub (<https://github.com/ucam-ceb-como/MOpS>) under an open source licence. All simulated structures are available to download from the University of Cambridge data repository (doi:10.17863/CAM.66055).

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